

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 947 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukxonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonaga eksportini oshishidagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	72
Z. Rahimova	
Влияние углеродного следа на экологическую устойчивость узбекистана.....	76
Саттарова Барно Шухратовна	
Moliya bozori dastaklari orqali xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish modellarining uslubiy asoslari.....	84
Ibragimov G'anijon G'ayratovich	
Maqsadli tushumlarning audit obyekti sifatidagi tasnifi va tavsifi.....	90
Ne'matov Oybek Ismatullayevich, Qambarov Abduazizbek	
Bank majburiyatlari tushunchasi, uning mazmuni va mohiyati.....	96
Muminova Parvina Ilhom qizi	
Sanoat korxonalariga berilayotgan soliq imtiyozlari ma'murchiligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar samaradorligi.....	100
Turabov Ulug'bek Olimjonovich	
Tur operatorlari va sayohat agentliklarida xarajatlar va foyda tahlili va uning turlari.....	106
Taniyev Ahmadjon Bahromovich	
O'zbekistonda kredit bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	113
Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich	
Social media marketing as a key strategy in modern business.....	125
Najimova Bakhtigul Abdilkasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda yashil mahsulotlar eksportini rivojlantirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish va xalqaro integratsiyani ta'minlash.....	129
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Оценка и управление рисками в проектах строительства энергетических объектов.....	136
Махматкулов Жамшед Бахтиёрович	
Iqtisodiyotda ko'chmas mulk bozori hamda uning xususiyatlari.....	140
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Raimkulov Sherali O'rozdavlatovich, G'ffarov Husayn Aliyor o'g'li, Ismoilov Davronjon Ilxomjon o'g'li, Tashpulatova Shaxnoza Tursunpulatovna	
Ekologik turizmning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'siri va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari (Jizzax viloyati misolida).....	144
Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.....	148
Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'ining budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati.....	152
Djabbarov Anvar Muxammadsaliyevich	

Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik reytingini aniqlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	157
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar auditini tashkil qilish masalalari	164
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich, Botirov Lazizbek Botirovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	168
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	174
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Strategic growth of global companies in contemporary environments.....	179
Djurabaev Otabek Djurabayevich	
Directions for management of the tax system.....	184
Sharokhmatov Abdurakhim Abdulamitovich	
Davlat korxonalarida moliyaviy samaradorlik va uni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	188
Qarshiyev Nodirbek Olim o'g'li	
Проблемы, модели и методы оптимизации управления товарными запасами	193
Бабаджанов Шопулат Шомашрабович	
Literature review: the significance of digitization to management credit activity of commercial banks	200
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining davlat budjeti.....	205
Ajibaeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot kontsepsiyasining shakillanishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari va uning dolzarbligi.....	212
Kodirov Javlonbek Nematullayevich	
Bank plastik kartalari orqali masofaviy xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	219
Abdullayeva Dildora Qudratovna, Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li, Almuratova Nurlio'lmasoy Naim qizi	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik modellashtirish	223
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Mahalla faoliyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	232
Aliqulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda lizing bozori tahlili.....	237
Boyev Bekzodjon Jo'raqul o'g'li, Shavkatov Behruz Rustam o'g'li	
Chakana savdoni rivojlantirishning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	241
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, tarkibiy tuzilish tasnifi va marketing segmentlari	244
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich	
Мировой опыт и перспективы развития свободно экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	250
Кадирова Истора Кадирова	
Перспективы реформирования налоговой системы Республики Узбекистан в условиях глобализации.....	254
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Садиков Искандар Гайратович	
O'zbekiston 2030 strategiyasi – islohotlar tizimligida ipoteka kreditining dolzarbligi.....	263
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	267
Shoraximova Zilola Nosirdjanovna	
Biologiya va tibbiyotda matematik statistika	271
Voxidov Alikul Melitoshevich	
Viloyatda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini o'tgan yilga nisbatan o'zgarishi.....	283
Azimov Allaberdin O'rinovich, Begaliyeva Madina Abdusamatovna	
Servis korxonalarida mobil ilovalar yordamida interaktiv xizmatlar yaratish	289
Ne'matov Nizom Ismatullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat ta'minot zanjiri tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	293
Nazarova A.N	

Влияние искусственного интеллекта при разработке стратегических программ на экономическое развитие страны.....	300
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
Kichik va o'rta biznesda moliyaviy menejment: muammolar va yechimlar	306
Saidvaliyeva Nigora Ziyodillayevna	
Теоретико-правовая характеристика экономических отношений	313
Фарход Махмудович Тиркашев, Исломжон Жамшедович Жамшедов	
Cash flow reporting in Uzbekistan: national accounting standards and international standards application	318
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	324
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Получение долгосрочного кредита и определение его размера для привлечения лизинга	330
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Ko'chmas mulk solig'ining ko'chmas mulk bozori tendensiyalariga ta'siri	335
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning davlat qarzi va uni boshqarishdagi tajribasini tahlil qilishga ilmiy yondashuv	343
Suynov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich, Abdurahmonova Feruzabonu	
Эффективный инновационный менеджмент в системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.....	353
Абдурахманов З.М.	
Islom moliyasining O'zbekistondagi o'rni va O'zbekiston Respublikasining islomiy tashkilotlar va banklar bilan aloqasi	356
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi, Elboyev Otajon Polvonquliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	361
Oxunjonova Madina Isoqjonovna	
Основные задачи обеспечения цифровой информационной безопасности в образовательном процессе	365
Иззатилла Пулатов Кудратиллаевич	
Tijorat banklarida komplaens nazoratni takomillashtirish.....	373
Muminova Marguba Mamirkulovna	
Kichik biznes uchun soliq imtiyozlari va ularning samaradorligi.....	378
Sarvar Ochilov	
Xalqaro moliyaviy tashkilotlarning davlat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni.....	387
Raxmonova Dildora Ergash qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kreditning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	395
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Mintaqa sanoat korxonalarida investitsiya jarayonlari rivojlanish tendensiyasining statistik tahlili.....	399
Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi	
Natijalarga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish samarali budjet menejmentining omili sifatida	403
N. Sheraliev	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznesning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari	408
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Features and prospects for the development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan.....	414
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Анализ динамики импорта узбекистана в 2017–2024 годах с учетом индекса сложности продукции (PCI)	418
Жабборова Нодира Холмурод кизи	
O'zbekistonning kredit riskini baholash: iqtisodiy barqarorlik va xavf omillari tahlili	422
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish – korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning muhim shartidir	426
Karimova Dilafuz Sadirdin qizi	

Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish omillari.....	431
Qo'ziyev Shodiyor Qilichboy o'g'li, Xakimov Javohir Hamza o'g'li, Turganbaev Nursultan Bayram o'g'li, Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich, Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich, Nurullayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность».....	437
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
Developing the labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment.....	442
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi, Elmurodov Mukhammadkodir Nurmuhammad	
Iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida raqamli texnologiyalar orqali qishloq xo'jaligida samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari.....	450
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Ochilov Ilhom Sayitqulovich, Sayfullayeva Ruxshona Farrux qizi	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning sanoatni rivojlantirishdagi roli.....	458
Samijonov Musobek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida risklarni boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	466
Muxitdinov Shuhrat Ziyavitdinovich	
Ovqatlanish xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlaridan foydalanish va samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	470
Ravshanov Zaxiriddin Ibragimovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	477
Safayeva Dilafruz Ruzmatovna, Karimov Abrorjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xarajatlarini rejalashtirish va moliyalashtirish: amaldagi holat tahlili.....	482
Bauyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T	
Tijorat banklarida foiz risklarini baholash va boshqarish.....	487
Karimov Mardon Akram o'g'li	
Zamonaviy sharoitda bank innovatsiyalaridan foydalanishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	494
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich	
A local perspective on sustainable supply chain management in Uzbekistan.....	501
Oybek Rafukjonkhajiev	
Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali sug'urta kompaniyalar marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish.....	505
Rashidova Dildora Rasul qizi	
O'zbekistonning strategik rivojlanish davrida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	511
Akbaraliyeva Aziza Maxmadali qizi	
O'zbekiston media bozori: rivojlanishi va afzalliklari.....	516
Qodirov Obidjon Olim o'g'li	
Порядок учета скидок в бухгалтерском учете на основе МСФО.....	520
Камолова Феруза Кахрамоновна	
Tijorat banklari transformatsiyasini amalga oshirishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida foydalanishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	525
Bobur Abrorovich Yusupov	
Neft va gaz sanoati korxonalarini resurslardan samarali foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari tahlili.....	533
Sonayev Sanjar Nurmatovich	
Оценка социально-экономического воздействия железнодорожных проектов.....	539
Хужаяров Бекзод Баходир угли	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda islom mikromoliyalashning innovatsion mexanizmlari va xalqaro tajriba.....	544
Sharipova Maxliyoxon Baxtiyor qizi	
Iqtisodiy samaradorlik tushunchasining ilmiy- nazariy tahlili.....	548
Ibragimov Zukhriddin Sayfutdinovich	
Ipoteka kreditlarini moliyalashtirishda banklarning o'rni va istiqbollari.....	552
Muhitdinov Ulug'bek Diyorovich	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini shakllanishining shart-sharoitlari, omillari, o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va prinsiplari.....	556
Amonov Navro'zxon Saloxiddin o'g'li	
Development of digital marketing for sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan.....	560
Nasibabonu Abdurakhmonovna Akramova	

Kichik biznes subyektlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	565
Ibragimov Ulmas	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning dolzarb masalalari	569
Akbarov Behzodxon Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Amerika qo'shma shtatlarida federal zaxira tizimi tomonidan amalga oshirilgan noan'anaviy pul-kredit siyosati.....	574
Djumonov Dilshod Safaroliyevich	
Intellectual mulkning ishlab chiqarishdagi ahamiyati	581
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashyev, Azizbek Umid o'g'li Abduvaliyev	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy barqarorligini baholashning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi	585
Sattarova Gulshan Muxiddinovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida moliyaviy xavfsizlik: investorlar misolida.....	589
Boysunov Jamshid Baxriddin ug'li	
Amaliy-ilmiy tadqiqotlarning mazmuni, asosiy maqsadlari va qo'llanilish shakllari.....	593
Raupov Jamshid Rashidovich, Kaxramonov Zafar Kaxramonovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	597
Ergashev Olim Kenjayevich	
Islom darchalari asosida moliyalashtirishni joriy etish istiqbollari	602
Gulyamova Shaxnoza Gafurdjanovna	
Влияние финансовых технологий на трансформацию страхового рынка.....	606
Тангирбердиева Гулчехра Рахимжановна	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlanishida mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotini holati tahlili	611
Muradova Maxliyoxon Ravshanovna	
Foreign experience in the formation of banking assets in improving the efficiency of the activities of commercial banks.....	615
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi ogli	
Роль и значение экономического потенциала в формировании стратегии регионов Узбекистана.....	628
Абдалова З.Т.	
Перспективы развития торговых отношений между Китаем и Узбекистаном.....	634
Фазлиддинова Шахруза, Расулев Дильмурод Мирза-Ахмедович	
Korxonalarda moliyaviy instrumentlarning hisobi va audit masalalarini rivojlantirish	640
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	647
Rajabov Alibek	
Digital technologies as a driver for the development of mice tourism in Uzbekistan	654
Ilkhomova Gulnoza Zaynitdin qizi	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining tashqi savdo faoliyati bojxona reytingini aniqlash va baholashning iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	661
Azizov Sherzod Uktamovich, Mamarajabov Abdisamad Saidmurot o'g'li	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlari	666
Shodiyev To'liqin Oltiboy o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalari rivojlanishining atrof-muhitga ta'sirini baholashda esg tamoyillarini qo'llash imkoniyatlari va istiqbollari	671
Turg'unov Jasurbek Alimardon o'g'li	
Museum collection management and new technology	677
Ibroximova Aziza Abbasovna	
Inklyuziyalashuv sharoitida sanoat korxonalari faoliyatining ilmiy-nazariy jihatlarini	684
Isayev Kobiljon Abdukodirovich	
Turizm sohasida brendning O'zbekiston iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri va sayyohlik yo'nalishi sifatida marketingning ahamiyati.....	693
Kobilova Maftuna	
Kichik biznes subyektlarida marketing faoliyatini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	697
Bektemirov Ozodjon Xusan o'g'li	
Tekislikda to'g'ri chiziq va uning tenglamalari.....	702
Azimova Hulkar Qayumovna	

Banking Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Practice and Reforms.....	707
Asliddin Qurvonboyev Baxrom o'g'li, Umarova Zulaykho	
Korxonalarda reklama faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli marketingdan foydalanish.....	712
Khojiev Elishod	
Необходимость использования искусственного интеллекта в системе образования – веление времени	717
Абдуллаханова Гулбахор Саттаровна	
Kon-metallurgiya kombinati faoliyatining ekonometrik modeli va uni rivojlantirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	721
Karimov Ma'ruf Ichthyorovich	
Ijara bo'yicha xalqaro standart qo'llanilishining xususiyatli jihatlari	725
Yusupova Malika Botiraliyeva, Satvaldiyeva Gulchexra Xudayberdiyeva	
Понятие и сущность маркетинговой деятельности малого бизнеса в Узбекистане.....	730
Убайдуллоева Малика Отабековна	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar tahlilini takomillashtirish	736
Ishonqulov Nizamjon Fayzullayevich, Mirzayeva Shaxlo Faxritdinovna	
Tijorat banklarida mavjud muammoli aktivlar miqdorini qisqartirish bo'yicha xorij mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	742
Abduxalimova Marjona Xikmatovna	
Bank strategiyasini shakllantirish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish (O'zsanoatqurilishbank misolida)	748
Maxmudova Munavarxon Ruzimuradovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatida parrandachilik tarmog'ini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	752
Ismoilov Zuhridin Sayitqulovich	
Yangi O'zbekistonda baholovchi tashkilotlar reytingini baholash va renkingini aniqlash mexanizmining tashkiliy va huquqiy asoslarini takomillashtirishning zarurligi.....	757
Tashpulatov Giyos Toxirovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida B2B marketing strategiyalarini tuzish va samaradorlikni belgilash.....	764
Yudashev Jamshid Abrarovich	
Iste'molchi xulq-atvori: marketing strategiyalarida uning o'rni.....	770
Hamidova Maftuna Boburjon qizi	
Impact of modern tourism infrastructure in enhancing a country's tourism potential.....	775
Ametova Shahnoza Rustamovna, Dauletbaeva Ulzada Bakhadirovna	
O'zbekistonda oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish va iste'moli tahlili	780
Umarov Ilxomjon Yuldashevich, Abdulxamidova Nodira Abdurashitovna	
Xalqaro tajriba asosida uy xo'jaliklarining investitsion faoliyatini rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	784
Berdiyev G'ayrat Ibragimovich	
O'zbekistonda elektroenergetika sohasi boshqaruvini tartibga solish masalalari	795
Samiev Shoxrux Faxriddin o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari eksportini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash yo'llari	801
Xaydarova Nargiza Anvarovna	
Greening Hotel Operations: A Framework for Sustainable Resource Management and Cost Efficiency in Bukhara Region.....	809
Toyirova Sarvinoz Atoevna, Canós-Darós, Lourdes, Osorio-Acosta, Estefanía	
O'zbekiston sanoat mahsulotlari eksportining tashqi bozorlar bilan o'zaro aloqalari	819
Yo'ldoshev Nozimbek Ma'rufjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy ta'lim eksportining rivojlanish tendensiyalari	824
Abdullayev Javoxir Jaxongirovich	
Dunyo oziq-ovqat bozorining dinamik rivojlanishidagi o'zgarishlar, qiyinchiliklar va ularning yechimlari	832
Tolipova Baxtigul Farxodovna	
Sanoat korxonalarida boshqarish jarayonlariga omillar ta'sirini baholash uslubiyotlari	836
D.Ziyayeva	
Zamonaviy firmalarda kommunikativ aloqalar tizimini o'rnatish bilan bog'liq muammolar	840
Sh.A.Suleymanova, Sh.Z.Erkinova	

Перспективы развития электронной коммерции Республики Узбекистан	845
<i>Маҳаммадалиева Муслимахон Шерали кизи</i>	
Surxondaryo viloyatida o'rtta muddatda uy-joylar qurilishi prognozlashtirishni tekshirish	851
<i>Ibragimov Nodir Shopo'latovich, Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Toshpo'latov Bobur Rasuljon o'g'li, Nuraliyeva Feruza Abdusalim qizi, Namozov Diyorbek Baxtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida dividend siyosatini takomillashtirish orqali investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish mexanizmlari.....	858
<i>Muxammadiyev Faxriddin Baxtiyorovich</i>	
O'zbekiston respublikasi budget daromadlarining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	861
<i>Shodiyev Xurshedjon Karimovich</i>	
Korxonalarda ishlab chikarish strategiyasini innovasion faoliyati orqali takomillashtirish yo'llari	865
<i>Fayzullayeva Aziza Nusratillayevna</i>	
Budget tashkilotlarining shtat jadvallarini tuzish va xarajatlar smetasi	871
<i>Xamdamov Nuriddin Abdimalikovich</i>	
Tax Revenues and Budget Allocation: The Impact of Tax Revenues on the Economy in Uzbekistan and Indonesia.....	875
<i>Vafoyeva Sevinch, Umarova Zulaykho</i>	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar – rivojlanishning muhim omili.....	879
<i>Axtamova Parizod Oybek qizi</i>	
The significance and impact of contemporary tourism infrastructure in boosting a country's tourism potential	883
<i>Matkabillova Diloram Khalilullayevna</i>	
Tijorat banklari investitsiya faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	887
<i>Abduvaliyev S.A.</i>	
Yangi iqtisodiy tizimda barqaror ish bilan bandlik konsepsiyasini ishlab chiqish va unga oid global tajribalar.....	892
<i>Xoliyorova Shoxista Qaxramon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagog-o'qituvchining innovatsion faoliyati modeliga asoslangan xolda ta'lim-tarbiya metodlari va vazifalarini o'rgatish.....	898
<i>Abdullaeva Sanobar Berdievna</i>	
O'zbekiston to'qimachilik klasterlari orqali iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash	903
<i>Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich</i>	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida moliyaviy hisobot ko'rsatkichlari tahlilining ilmiy asoslari	909
<i>G.J.Jumayeva</i>	
Интеграция современных концепций управленческого учета в учетно-аналитическую практику вузовских научных учреждений в Узбекистане.....	912
<i>Каршиева Мохинур Олим кизи</i>	
O'zbekiston sug'urta amaliyotida umr davomiyligi funksiyalarini aniqlashda aktuar hisoblarning o'rni.....	916
<i>Abdujalilova Guzal Saydillayevna</i>	
Инструменты фондового рынка в международной практике повышения инвестиционной привлекательности бизнеса	921
<i>Юлдуз Усманова</i>	
O'zbekiston respublikasi moliya-kredit tizimidagi muammolari va ustuvor yo'nalish istiqbollari.....	931
<i>Olimov Abror Axadjon o'g'li</i>	
O'zbekistonning fiskal va monetar siyosati tashqi savdo defitsiti o'sishiga ta'siri.....	935
<i>Baxtiyorov Sherali Muzaffarovich</i>	
The accounting system in trade organizations, as well as the classification of income in trade.....	941
<i>Qurbonov Tolmasjon Namoz o'g'li, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o'g'li, Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich</i>	

According to Kaplan and Atkinson (1998), accounting systems in trade organizations must integrate both financial and managerial accounting practices. The integration allows for accurate financial reporting, as well as for internal management control. For instance, trade-specific systems must support detailed inventory management, cash flow tracking, and receivables management.

In a more localized context, Uzbek scholars such as Yuldashev (2019) have emphasized the transformation of accounting systems in trade under the influence of international financial reporting standards (IFRS). As Uzbekistan integrates into global economic systems, the adaptation of modern accounting technologies and transparent reporting practices is increasingly important.

Income classification in trade is another widely discussed topic in accounting literature. The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) defines income as increases in economic benefits in the form of inflows or enhancements of assets. In trade organizations, income primarily arises from the sale of goods, and is categorized into operating income (main business activities) and non-operating income (secondary activities such as rent or dividends).

According to Weygandt, Kimmel, and Kieso (2018)¹, trade income can be classified based on its source and periodicity:

- Primary income: from the sale of goods and services.
- Secondary income: from ancillary operations such as service charges, leasing, or promotional fees.
- Extraordinary income: from infrequent and unusual events, though such classification is limited under modern IFRS.

Some researchers argue for a more granular classification in trade-specific contexts. For example, Berman and Evans (2015) discuss retail income streams, including revenue from store operations, online channels, and cross-promotional arrangements. In emerging markets like Uzbekistan, Mamatkulov (2021) suggests a classification adapted to mixed trade operations where both wholesale and retail sales are present.

While the global literature is rich with theoretical models and best practices, there is a relative lack of region-specific research tailored to the legal and economic context of Central Asia. This includes a need for detailed frameworks addressing how trade organizations in transition economies adjust their accounting systems amid digitalization, tax reforms, and IFRS adoption.

Moreover, current literature tends to emphasize corporate or large-scale trade enterprises, often neglecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which dominate the trade sector in many developing countries, including Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative research methods to comprehensively examine accounting systems and income classification practices in trade organizations, with a focus on both international frameworks and their application in the context of Uzbekistan.

The research is exploratory and analytical in nature. It aims to:

1. Identify prevailing accounting practices in trade organizations.
2. Analyze the structure and classification of income.
3. Evaluate the extent to which international accounting standards are implemented in trade enterprises, particularly within Uzbekistan.

The study relies on extensive secondary data obtained from:

- Academic journals and books on accounting theory.
- Reports by international organizations such as the IASB and IFAC.
- National regulations and guidelines from the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Financial statements and annual reports of trade enterprises.
- Statistical data from the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan.

- Primary data is collected through:

- Structured interviews with accounting professionals, financial managers, and auditors in trade organizations.
- Surveys distributed among small, medium, and large trade enterprises to gather data on accounting system usage and income categorization.
- The survey includes both closed and open-ended questions to capture numerical data and qualitative insights.

Qualitative data from interviews is analyzed through content analysis, identifying recurring themes, terminologies, and practices in accounting and income classification.

¹ https://books.google.ru/books/about/Accounting_Principles.html?id=ZSaVDwAAQBAJ&redir_esc=y

Quantitative data from surveys is processed using descriptive statistics (mean, frequency, percentage) and comparative analysis to identify trends in system adoption and classification schemes.

Additionally, a case study approach is used to examine 2–3 representative trade enterprises in depth, analyzing their accounting software, reporting format, and compliance with national and international standards.

All participants were informed of the study's purpose and gave their consent before interviews or surveys. Confidentiality of enterprise and participant data is strictly maintained, and the data is used solely for academic purposes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Trade is an enterprise that has a direct classification of enterprises and enterprises. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, an investigation is underway.

“Trade - primarily refers to economic relations related to the sale of goods, and economic relations arising in the process of commodity exchange. Secondly, as a branch of the economy, it is a complex of trading enterprises that have become independent as a result of the social division of labor”². “While trade has long been a source of profit, culture in all countries of the world was considered a means of education. Trading activity is not only a special kind of activity, but also represents a special branch of the economy.

Trade as an activity is a type of entrepreneurship carried out by legal entities and individuals. Since they are participants in the process of buying and selling goods, it is believed that they connect the sphere of production with the sphere of consumption. For this reason, products created without sale do not reach their consumers and their reproduction is impossible”³.

Based on the viewpoints expressed by scholars discussed above, it can be concluded that trade, as a phenomenon, represents the system of economic relations that emerge during the distribution process. It encompasses the operations of trading enterprises, defines individual commercial networks, and plays a crucial role in delivering goods to end consumers.

With the transition to a market-oriented economy, the social structure, as well as the organizational and economic classification of trade, underwent profound transformations. During the Soviet era, the trade system in the republic consisted predominantly of state-owned trade, cooperative trade, and collective farm markets. However, following the shift in ownership structures and the ensuing process of decentralization, state trade was almost entirely privatized. Its contribution to the overall trade turnover diminished significantly, falling to merely 1%. Similarly, cooperative trade was privatized, retaining approximately 9% of the market share. As for the collective farm markets, they ceased to exist and were replaced by newly established peasant markets.

Consequently, a fundamentally new form of trade emerged – private trade – which led to a complete overhaul of property-based trade forms. This development paved the way for the establishment of a non-governmental sector that now dominates the trading sphere (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Classification of commercial enterprises by their legal status⁴.

2 Абдукаримов Б.А. Ички савдо иқтисодиёти. Дарслик. 1-қисм. – Т.: Фан ва технология, 2007, 39-бет.

3 Уразов К.Б. Бошқа тармоқларда бухгалтерия ҳисобининг хусусиятлари. Маърузалар матни. 1-қисм. – Самарқанд, СамИСИ, 2005, 5-бет.

4 Меъёрий ҳужжатлар талаблари асосида муаллиф ишланмаси.

Trading enterprises primarily specialize in the procurement and subsequent sale of goods, forming the foundation of the economic activity of commodity producers. In this context, commodity operators refer to the economic personnel of trading entities who are directly involved in purchasing goods and organizing their sale. As a result, commodity transactions encompass a wide array of interconnected processes, beginning with the initial receipt of goods and concluding with their transfer to the next buyer, which may include another trading enterprise or the final consumer.

The operational activity of trading enterprises can be structurally segmented into three main stages:

1. Procurement stage – this initial phase involves operations such as receiving goods from supplier organizations, increasing inventory levels, transporting goods, conducting settlements with suppliers, intermediary agents, and logistics firms, as well as complying with customs procedures for imported products.

2. Storage stage – at this stage, goods are delivered to warehouse facilities where they are sorted by quality or grade, processed as necessary, packed, and dispatched for further distribution based on storage and logistical needs.

3. Sales implementation stage – widely regarded as the most critical stage of trading operations, this phase entails active promotion of goods through marketing and advertising, establishing sales contracts with customers, organizing the shipment of goods, and carrying out financial settlements with clients.

In terms of how trade transactions are accounted for and executed, trade is commonly classified into wholesale and retail forms. This classification is determined by the nature of the buyer, transaction volume, and the trade's positioning within the distribution chain.

A significant theoretical consideration in the income analysis of trading enterprises lies in the classification of income. This process involves segmenting income into distinct categories based on their functional designation and determining the specific components included within each income type. Such classification provides a structured framework for evaluating the financial performance and revenue structure of trading entities.

Some literature claims that their income comes from non-sales activities and non-sale of goods, from non-aligned activities⁵. Although the authors of these books do not calculate exactly what is included in non-analytical income, the purchase, which is the result of the main activity of trading enterprises, includes all other income in non-analytical income, in addition to the sale of goods.

"In the textbook "Economics of Trade", the gross income of trading enterprises is divided into income from core activities, income from non-residential fund and other income⁶. In this tutorial, income from the sale of goods was considered as income from core activities, as non-analytical income, such as fines imposed, pensions, penalties, surplus goods and the origin of the debtor's debts that were previously written off. All income not listed in the list is included in the "other income" group.

K.B.Urazov and M.B. Annaev reflected the income of the enterprise by type of activity in their own way (Tables 1).

Table 1. Classification of the company's income by type of activity⁷.

Income groups	Types of income included in the report
1. Income from the sale of products, goods, business services	1. Net revenue from the sale of products. 2. Net proceeds from the sale of goods. 3. Net proceeds from the sale of completed works. 4. Net proceeds from the sale of course services
2. Income from investment activities	1. Income in the form of interest. 2. Earnings on Kura in the form of dividends. 3. Benefits derived from the use of materials, tools and other chemicals. 4. Profit from the sale of intangible assets and other expenses. 5. Profit from the sale of unfinished capital investments and other expenses 6. Profit from the sale of financial investments and other expenses. 7. Profit from the sale of items for cocktails and other delights. 8. Net proceeds from Kiska long-term lease 9. Net long-term rental income

5 Экономика предприятия. Под ред. В.Я.Горфинкеля, В.А.Швандера. 3-изд. Учебник. – М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2001, ст. 570., Додобоев Ю.Т., Зикряев Э. и др. Экономика предприятия. Учебник. – Т., 1998, 177-б. ва бошқ.

6 Мухаммедов М.М. и др. Экономика торговли. Уч. пос. – Самарканд, СамКИ, 1998, ст. 258.

7 Уразов К.Б. Иқтисодий эркинлаштириш шароитида бухгалтерия ҳисобининг концептуал масалалари. Монография. - Т.: Фан, 2005, 234 – б;
Аннаев М.Б. Савдо корхоналарида даромадлар ҳисоби ва аудитининг долзарб масалалари. Монография. - Т.: Наврўз, 2011. - 138 бет.

3. Income from financial activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Positive exchange rate differences for currency schemes. 2. Collected or accrued fines and pensions. 3. Profit from material and other expenses. 4. Government subsidies. 5. Financial assistance received in the absence of skidding. 6. Other income related to financial activities.
4. Other income from nationwide activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Income from auxiliary farms and enterprises providing services. 2. Income from revaluation of TMBs. 3. Profit from previous years determined in the reporting year. 4. Orthopedic products with aniline in the inventory. 5. Extraordinary income. 6. Other operating income.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, in the article we made the assumption that in order to organize the accounting and reporting of income in chambers of commerce and create carelessness in recognizing income and attracting investors, it is necessary to further improve national standards and adapt them to international standards, and the following proposals were put forward.

The study reveals that the accounting systems used in trade organizations play a crucial role in ensuring accurate financial reporting, operational efficiency, and compliance with both national and international standards. Effective accounting systems enable trade enterprises to track inventory, manage cash flows, and classify income correctly, which is especially critical in a highly dynamic and competitive trade environment.

The classification of income in trade organizations remains a complex issue, particularly due to the diversity of revenue sources and transaction types. While many large enterprises follow International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), smaller businesses often lack standardized approaches, leading to inconsistencies in income recognition and reporting.

In Uzbekistan, significant progress has been made in aligning national accounting practices with global standards. However, challenges remain in terms of technology adoption, professional training, and regulatory enforcement, especially among small and medium-sized trade enterprises.

As a result of our research on this topic, we offer the following proposals to improve the level of digital security in Uzbekistan:

- It can be a complex of one type (single-element) and several elements (general production costs, period costs, etc.), consisting of one element (materials, wages, etc.), depending on the composition of income and expenses;
- Introduction of synthetic accounts in the work account plan for each type of income;
- Adapt the account and report to the requirements of international standards;
- Standardization of Accounting Practices
- Implementation of Modern Accounting Software
- Training and Capacity Building
- Regulatory Support and Incentives
- Enhanced Transparency and Audit Practices
- Further Research

List of used literature:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2016 йил 27 декабрдаги «Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2017 йилги асосий макроиқтисодий кўрсаткичлари прогнози ва Давлат бюджети параметрлари тўғрисида»ги ПҚ-2699-сонли Қарори.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида»ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 7 февралдаги ПФ-4947-сонли Фармони. «Халқ сўзи» газетасининг 2017 йил 8 февралдаги 28 (6722)-сони.Ўзбекистон.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 1999 йил 5 февралдаги 54-сон қарори билан тасдиқланган «Маҳсулот (ишлар, хизматлар) ни ишлаб чиқариш ва сотиш харажатларининг таркиби ҳамда молиявий натижаларни шакллантириш таркиби тўғрисида»ги Низом.
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 24 февралда ПҚ-4611 «Молиявий ҳисоботнинг халқаро стандартларига ўтиш бўйича қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида»ги қарори.
5. Экономика предприятия. Под ред. В.Я.Горфинкеля, В.А.Швандера. 3-изд. Учебник. – М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2001, ст. 570., Додобоев Ю.Т., Зикряев Э. и др. Экономика предприятия. Учебник. – Т., 1998, 177-б. ва бошқ.
6. Мухаммедов М.М. и др. Экономика торговли. Уч. пос. – Самарканд, СамКИ, 1998, ст. 258.

7. Уразов К.Б. Иқтисодийни эркинлаштириш шароитида бухгалтерия ҳисобининг концептуал масалалари. Монография. - Т.: Фан, 2005, 234 – б;
8. Аннаев М.Б. Савдо корхоналарида даромадлар ҳисоби ва аудитининг долзарб масалалари. Монография. - Т.: Наврӯз, 2011. – 138 бет.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
